

Amperometric determination of nitrite with a carbon paste electrode using covalently immobilized thionin

K. Thenmozhi^a and S. Sriman Narayanan^{*b}

^aEnvironmental and Analytical Chemistry Division, School of Advanced Sciences,
Vellore Institute of Technology University, Vellore-632 014, Tamilnadu, India

^bDepartment of Analytical Chemistry, University of Madras, Guindy Campus, Chennai-600 025, India

E-mail : sriman55@gmail.com

Abstract : A covalent immobilization procedure for the phenothiazine redox mediator thionin using functionalized graphite powder as the immobilization matrix was developed. A carbon paste electrode constructed from this modified graphite powder served as a novel sensor for nitrite determination. The method of covalent immobilization of the mediator proved to be effective in anchoring the water soluble mediator for electrochemical studies. The modified electrode exhibited electrocatalytic activity for the reduction of nitrite at lesser potential with high sensitivity. The amperometric sensor can measure nitrite in the linear range from $1.66 \times 10^{-5} M$ to $3.13 \times 10^{-3} M$ with a correlation coefficient of 0.9966 and a detection limit of $1.17 \times 10^{-5} M$. Remarkable advantages of this electrode are its ease of fabrication, surface renewability, reproducibility and reasonable stability.

Keywords : Thionin, carbon paste electrode, covalent immobilization, nitrite.

Introduction

Nitrite (NO_2^-) plays a vital role in life processes as well as environment. Nitrite is one of the parameters involved in the determination of nitrogen fixation, denitrification, sedimentation and many other man-made processes that could reflect on the quality of natural, surface and underground waters^{1,2}. The presence of excess nitrite in drinking water, fruits, vegetables, and other food products is a major threat to human health. So the determination of nitrite is vital in industrial, physiological and environmental fields. Several methods have been reported for the quantitative determination of nitrite including capillary electrophoresis³, spectrophotometry⁴ and fluorescence⁵. These methods are sensitive, but most of them require a laborious sample pretreatment, sophisticated performance and costly equipment. Electrochemical methods have proven to be useful alternative since they are simple, speedy and achieve low detection limit offering rapid response times apart from ease of miniaturization^{6,7}.

Chemically modified electrodes have the ability to catalyze either the oxidation or reduction of the species, which require a high overpotential at the unmodified electrodes⁸⁻¹⁰. Chemically modified carbon paste electrodes (CPEs) are prepared traditionally by mixing the mediator, graphite and pasting liquid. Hence the mediators used for direct mixing should be insoluble in analytic solution and be strongly adsorbed by carbon such that the dissolution of the mediator from the electrode surface would be completely avoided during measurements. This restricts the number of available and usable redox mediators for electrode modification. On the other hand, a number of water soluble redox mediators are available which could not be employed as mediators since they may not adhere to the surface when in contact with aqueous solution.

Hence an attempt has been made in this work to covalently immobilize a redox mediator with graphite powder, so that a water soluble redox mediator can be used for electrode preparation. The mediator chosen for this work is thionin (TH), a water soluble phenothiazine dye

containing two primary amino groups. The mediator is immobilized to graphite powder using the amino group of thionin, to achieve a bulk modified graphite that can be used for carbon paste electrode preparation. This will render the effective use of thionin as a redox mediator without any associated leaching problem and the carbon paste electrode developed from thionin immobilized graphite powder has satisfactory physical and chemical stability. Nitrite determination has been chosen as an example to illustrate the utility of the thionin modified carbon paste electrode (TH-CPE) in static as well as dynamic conditions.

Experimental

Thionin was purchased from Himedia. Graphite powder (1–2 micron) was received from Sigma Aldrich. All other chemicals employed were of analytical grade and used as received. Electrochemical experiments were performed with a CHI 400A Electrochemical Analyzer in a conventional three electrode cell. Thionin modified carbon paste electrode was used as working electrode, a platinum wire as counter electrode and saturated calomel electrode (SCE) as the reference electrode.

For the covalent immobilization of the mediator, the graphite powder was first oxidized to introduce carboxyl functional groups. 6 g of graphite powder was refluxed with 150 ml of 5 M HNO₃ for 7 h. This oxidized graphite powder was washed thoroughly to bring the pH to 7.00 and dried in an oven at 150 °C for 13 h¹³. Subsequent conversion of carboxylic groups to acid chloride was carried out using thionyl chloride. 5 g of oxidized graphite was refluxed for 5 h with 20 ml of 5% SOCl₂ in toluene. Extensive washing to remove excess thionyl chloride was done with toluene and dried in an oven at 150 °C for 13 h¹³. Immobilization of the mediator was carried out as follows : 30 mg of thionin was refluxed with 2 g of functionalized graphite powder in 50 ml of DMF for 12 h to allow the primary amino groups on the mediator to react with the acid chloride to form an amide linkage. The graphite powder was washed thoroughly with DMF to remove unreacted dye and finally with isopropanol and then dried at room temperature for 4 h. The modified carbon paste electrode was constructed using thionin immobilized graphite powder and silicone oil. 30 mg of

thionin immobilized graphite powder was stirred thoroughly with 30 μL of silicone oil to form a homogeneous paste, which was then packed into the cavity of a glass tube (*ca.* 2 mm i.d) and electrical contact was provided on the other end by forcing a copper wire. The electrode obtained in this manner was smoothed over the weighing paper and used as working electrode.

Results and discussion

The electrochemical characterization of the TH-CPE was carried out using cyclic voltammetry. The cyclic voltammogram of TH-CPE obtained in 0.1 M NH₄NO₃ at a potential scan rate of 20 mV s⁻¹ is shown in Fig. 1 (Inset, curve b). On scanning the potential in the range of 0.2 to -0.6 V, the modified electrode exhibited a pair of redox peaks with formal potential, $E^{0'}$ ($E^{0'} = (E_{pa} + E_{pc})/2$) of about -0.226 V, with cathodic peak potential at -0.266 V and anodic peak potential at -0.186 V, corresponding to the immobilized mediator. The formal potential of TH in the modified electrode differed from that of TH in solution (-0.231 V) due to the covalent immobilization of the mediator¹². The unmodified CPE did not show any characteristic reaction under similar condition (Fig. 1, Inset, curve a). Effect of scan rate on the performance of the TH-CPE was also evaluated. Both the cathodic and anodic peak currents were found to increase

Fig. 1. CVs of (a) unmodified CPE, (b) 1.62×10^{-4} M nitrite at unmodified CPE, (c) TH-CPE, (d) 1.62×10^{-4} M nitrite at TH-CPE in 0.1 M NH₄NO₃ (0.05 M phosphate buffer, pH 7.0); scan rate : 20 mV s⁻¹. Inset : CVs of (a) unmodified CPE, (b) TH-CPE.

upon increasing the scan rate (Fig. 2). A linear relation was observed between the peak currents and the square root of scan rate and the results indicate that the redox reaction involves a diffusion controlled process at the electrode surface.

Fig. 2. CVs of TH-CPE in 0.1 M NH₄NO₃ at different scan rates: (a) 20, (b) 50, (c) 100, (d) 150 and (e) 200 mV s⁻¹.

The voltammetric response for the reduction of nitrite at the modified TH-CPE and at the unmodified CPE is shown in Fig. 1. The curves a and c correspond to unmodified CPE and TH-CPE respectively in 0.1 M NH₄NO₃ (pH 7.00, 0.05 M phosphate buffer) in the absence of nitrite. Owing to high overpotential requirement for the reduction of nitrite at most electrodes, addition of 1.62 × 10⁻⁴ M nitrite to the electrolytic solution showed a poor response with a small current response at very high potentials at the unmodified CPE. In contrast, a prominent increase in cathodic current was observed for the same concentration of nitrite at a reduced potential of -0.3 V at the modified electrode. The increase in current response at lesser overpotential observed for the reduction of nitrite at the modified electrode compared to the unmodified electrode reveals the electrocatalytic effect of the immobilized mediator.

In order to optimize the working potential for nitrite determination in flow systems, hydrodynamic voltammetry studies were performed. The cathodic current response was measured at constant intervals of applied potential, for 1.62 × 10⁻⁴ M nitrite solution in the potential range of 0.2 to -0.6 V. The results from hydrodynamic

voltammetry are shown in Fig. 3 and are in agreement with those from cyclic voltammetry. As can be seen from the Figure, the current at the unmodified electrode is not significant for nitrite detection. In contrast, at the modified electrode an enhanced current is observed which starts even at 0 V. On increasing the cathodic potential, the response rose sharply near -0.32 V. Hence, the modified electrode permits convenient detection of nitrite at lower potentials with high sensitivity due to its electrocatalytic activity.

Fig. 3. Hydrodynamic voltammograms of 1.62 × 10⁻⁴ M nitrite at (a) unmodified CPE, (b) TH-CPE in 0.1 M NH₄NO₃ (0.05 M phosphate buffer, pH 7.0); stirring rate : 300 rpm.

Chronoamperometric experiments have been carried out for the determination of nitrite and the optimum potential of -0.32 V was selected from the hydrodynamic voltammetric experiment. Amperometric response was recorded for successive injection of 1 ml of 1 mM nitrite to 0.1 M NH₄NO₃ at pH 7.00. The sensor exhibited a rapid and sensitive response to the changes in nitrite concentrations, which is attributed to the high electrocatalytic activity of the covalently immobilized thionin. The reduction current increases with every addition of nitrite and quickly reaches a stable value (< 5 s) indicating the short response time of the sensor for nitrite determination. Fig. 4 shows the part of the chronoamperogram recorded for nitrite in the concentration range of 1.66 × 10⁻⁵ M to 1.47 × 10⁻⁴ M and the inset displayed the corresponding calibration plot. The sensor showed good amperometric response for nitrite determination with lin-

Fig. 4. Chronoamperometric response at TH-CPE for each addition of 1 ml of 1 mM nitrite to 0.1 M NH_4NO_3 ; pH 7.00 (0.05 M phosphate buffer); stirring rate : 300 rpm. Inset : Calibration graph for nitrite measurement.

earity upto 2.35×10^{-3} M. Thus TH-CPE electrode has very good mediating properties and promotes the amperometric determination of nitrite at very less potential.

Conclusion

Graphite powder was covalently functionalized with thionin, a phenothiazine mediator and used as the electrode material to fabricate a chemically modified carbon paste electrode. A stable and surface renewable electrode with the mediator covalently attached to the matrix to control leaching problems has been designed. It has been demonstrated that the immobilized thionin could act as an effective catalyst for the cathodic reduction of nitrite at reduced overpotential. The modified electrode permits a convenient detection of nitrite with the linear range span-

ning from 1.66×10^{-5} M to 3.13×10^{-3} M. The immobilization strategy proved to be efficient in retaining the water soluble mediator to the electrode surface, resulting in good operational and storage stability. This work demonstrates the feasibility of constructing an amperometric sensor using thionin as an example, but the procedure can be extended to other water soluble mediators.

References

1. Y. Astier, G. W. Canters, J. J. Davis, H. A. O. Hill, M. P. Verbeet and H. J. Wijma, *Chem. Phys. Chem.*, 2005, **6**, 1114.
2. B. Strehlitz, B. Grundig, W. Schumacher, P. M. H. Kroneck, K.-D. Vorlop and H. Kotte, *Anal. Chem.*, 1996, **68**, 807.
3. B. Y. Erdogan and A. N. J. Onar, *Food Drug Anal.*, 2012, **20**, 532.
4. N. Pourreza, M. R. Fathi and A. Hatami, *Microchem. J.*, 2012, **104**, 22.
5. L. L. Wang, B. Li, L. M. Zhang, L. G. Zhang and H. F. Zhao, *Sens. Actuators (B)*, 2012, **171**, 946.
6. T. Hiratsu, H. Suzuki and K. Yamaguchi, *Chem. Commun.*, 2005, 4534.
7. D. Quan and W. Shin, *Sensors*, 2010, **10**, 6241.
8. S. Senthil Kumar, K. Kwak and D. Lee, *Electroanalysis*, 2011, **23**, 2116.
9. R. N. Goyal and S. Bishnoi, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2012, **51**, 205.
10. S. Senthil Kumar, G. Baek, S. Lee, C.-H. Jun and D. Lee, *Electrochem. Commun.*, 2012, **19**, 123.
11. B. J. Privett, J. H. Shin and M. H. Schoenfisch, *Anal. Chem.*, 2010, **82**, 4723.
12. H. Y. Chen, D. M. Zhou, J. J. Xu and H. Q. Fang, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1997, **422**, 21.
13. A. R. Silva, M. Martins, M. M. A. Freitas, A. Valente, C. Freire, B. de Castro and J. L. Figueiredo, *Micropor. Mesopor. Mater.*, 2002, **55**, 275.